

RETURN Project – Proof of Concept (PoC) Report of Spoke VS3 on Volcanic Risk

PoC Title: An Integrated Multidimensional Risk Framework for highly populated areas: the test case of Mt. Vesuvius, Italy

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1. Summary

The scope of the PoC is the obtainment of risk maps that include both physical hazard, social and physical vulnerability, social and building exposure.

The challenge that the PoC addresses is the difficulty of standardizing data from physical hazard with those of vulnerability and exposure (which are expressed in diverse metrics), and implement a synthetic index that shows the risk distribution over the area of interest. The innovative idea is the use of multivariate statistics of the type of Principal Component Analysis and factor Analysis for obtaining an ensemble risk index coupled with cartographic techniques that allow merging the risk components

2. Objectives

The main aim of the PoC is to develop and test a methodology that integrates data coming from the diverse components of the “risk equation” – Hazard, vulnerability and exposure – and allows standardization of the metrics of the multitude of variables involved, as to obtain risk maps, which show the spatial distribution of risk in densely populated areas subject to a significant hazard.

The test carried out on the pyroclastic flow risk at Vesuvius contributes to the goals of the VS3 spoke (Earthquakes and Volcanoes) and, by means of the generalization of the multivariate statistical method, it is of interest of the general RETURN Project.

3. The test Case of Mount Vesuvius

Mt. Vesuvius is widely known as one of the most dangerous volcanoes because of the likelihood of future explosive eruptions in a densely populated area (Gurioli et al., 2010; Lirer et al., 2010; Baxter, 2008), which could affect large territories. It is well known that disaster risk depends on the severity of hazard, the number of people or assets exposed and the vulnerability or susceptibility of these elements to suffer loss and damage (UNDRR, 2022). As a consequence, when large populations or significant assets are exposed to volcanic hazards and show high vulnerability, the likelihood of risk escalating into disaster increases. This progression is driven not by the frequency or magnitude of the hazard itself, but by the territorial context—namely demographic, social, economic, and building structural conditions. For this reason, volcanic hazards and disasters have unique characteristics when compared with other natural hazards that require special consideration in risk assessment (Lowe, 2010). The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, clearly recognizes that disaster risk management needs to be about managing the risk inherent in social and economic activity, rather than simply mainstreaming disaster risk management to protect against external threats like natural hazards (CRED & UNDRR,

2020). Consequently, combining volcanic hazard, demographic, social and building characteristics to understand the level of risk is crucial to manage disaster risk in highly populated areas such as the Mt. Vesuvius.

Over the past two decades, several studies have attempted to integrate hazard, exposure, and vulnerability in volcanic settings worldwide (Córdoba et al., 2025; Sparks et al., 2025; Muryani et al., 2024; Nieto-Torres et al., 2023, 2021; Bonadonna et al., 2021; Guimarães et al., 2021; Reyes-Hardy et al., 2021; Jumadi et al., 2020). In the Vesuvius area, however, research mainly addressed individual components of risk—generally one or two at a time—such as exposure and hazard (Alberico et al., 2011); building exposure and physical vulnerability (Zuccaro & De Gregorio, 2019, 2013; Spence et al., 2004); overall vulnerability (Willis et al., 2014); population exposure and social vulnerability (Pesaresi et al., 2008); hazard assessment (Dellino et al., 2025; Sulpizio et al., 2018; Rolandi, 2010; Marzocchi et al., 2004); or focusing on risk perception (Avvisati et al., 2019; Ricci et al., 2013; Carlino et al., 2008). A further challenge lies in conducting risk analyses at the local level, where the lack of high-resolution spatial demographic and socio-economic census data (Lapietra et al., 2025) hampers comprehensive planning and necessitates spatial assessments that integrate place-specific hazard characteristics with demographic, social, and economic conditions at the enumeration area scale (Buck & Summers, 2020). These aspects underline the need to use an approach that covers all the aspects of risk in this area that have not previously been examined through multidisciplinary approaches at the local level and more in general for the development of volcanology (Doronzo et al., 2022).

The test case application of the PoC focuses therefore on combining and mapping of (i) volcanic hazard, (ii) exposure, (iii) vulnerability and (iv) volcanic risk in the Mt. Vesuvius area at enumeration area (EA) level in order to retrieve information about (v) inhabitants and buildings, located on areas at different risk levels as to provide useful information for cost-benefit analysis, land-use planning and risk mitigation.

The volcano is currently in a state of quiescence, marked solely by fumarolic activity and low seismicity, but it is continuously monitored by the surveillance network of the Vesuvius Observatory, the Naples branch of the Italian National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (INGV).

In terms of risk management, the National Civil Protection Department (CPD), carries out activities of forecasting, prevention, and mitigation of volcanic risk in Italy and adopts measures aimed at reducing the loss of human lives and property in the event of an eruption. The authority, that is also responsible for overseeing the phases of emergency management and recovery, with the efforts of the Campania Region defined the National Emergency Plans for the Vesuvius area consisting of two zones (Figure 1b). The red zone, covering 25 municipalities, includes the area exposed to pyroclastic flows (Red Zone 1) and the territory at high risk of roof collapse due to the accumulation of pyroclastic deposits (Red Zone 2). The yellow zone, comprising of 63 municipalities and three districts of the City of Naples, represents the area exposed to significant fallout of volcanic ash and pyroclastic material. Although this is the most recent official document for emergency planning and evacuation for the Vesuvius area, the red zone map does not take into account the impact that PDCs could have on buildings and people that required the distribution of the impact parameters (flow temperature, flow duration, particle concentration and flow dynamic pressure) that better represent flow intensity in terms of damage potential over the volcano's surroundings (Dellino et al., 2025). These parameters, that have been addressed by Mele

et al. (2024), are essential to build long-term volcanic hazard mapping for risk analysis in the Vesuvius area and represents the starting point of this research.

Figure 1 Geographic setting of Mt Vesuvius within the national context (A), a zoom at the local level (B) and the municipalities included in the Civil Protection National Plan of volcanic risk (C). The regional and municipality boundaries were retrieved from the Italian National Statistical Institute (ISTAT) dataset, while Google Satellite was used as basemap.

3. Methods and Tools

The PoC development consists of the application of an integrated multidimensional framework for risk analysis based upon the definition provided by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), which describes risk as the product of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability (UNDRR, 2022). Specifically, the research explores the relationship between long-term volcanic hazard (pyroclastic density currents, PDCs), human population features (population exposure and social vulnerability) and building characteristics (building exposure and physical vulnerability). In our case, volcanic hazard can be defined as the probability of long-term occurrence of PDCs to damage a territory in a specified period of time. According to Marzocchi et al. (2004), the consideration of long-term volcanic hazards is very useful for cost/benefit analysis of risk mitigation actions, and for appropriate land use planning and location of settlements. Population and building

exposure represent the number of people and buildings exposed to long-term volcanic hazard; while social and physical vulnerability can be described as the combination of demographic, socioeconomic factors and building characteristics that can (potentially) increase the impacts of the element exposed.

The methodology has been constructed with the aim of assessing volcanic risk in the Vesuvius area by analyzing, mapping and combining hazard, exposure and vulnerability (section 1) at EA level. As shown in table 1, in order to assess long-term volcanic hazard, four main variables linked to the impact parameters of pyroclastic flows were retrieved from Mele et al. (2024). These parameters are detailed discussed in Dellino et al., 2025 and represent the PDCs flow characteristics useful for evaluating the damaging capacity.

In the case of exposure, linked to population and buildings located in the possibly affected areas, the number of inhabitants of each enumeration areas were collected from the Italian National Statistical Institute (ISTAT) dataset, while the building structural aggregates shapefile was retrieved from the Civil Protection Department (DPC) repository. Both databases refer to the year 2021.

As regards the evaluation of social vulnerability, 8 main variables explaining the demographic and socioeconomic condition of each enumeration area were collected from the 2021 ISTAT dataset, while data about buildings structural characteristics and housing conditions were retrieved from 2011 Census ISTAT dataset (currently the most recent for buildings). It is essential to highlight that, taking into account that there is no guideline concerning which data to use and how to treat this data for the construction of the vulnerability indexes (Frigerio et al., 2016), the choice of these variables is strictly linked to the most recent literature that underline the significant factors influencing social and physical vulnerability, data availability at enumeration area level and the socio-economic characteristics of the Campania population. Particularly, social vulnerability was expressed in terms of: percentages of individuals under 15 and over 76 years old, households with more than four members, foreign residents, unemployed males and females, and the share of male and female with at most a lower secondary education (low human capital). Physical vulnerability was instead evaluated by considering the type of building (residential or commercial), the construction material (masonry or other), the year of construction (before 1980), the number of floors (more than 4) and the state of preservation (poor and very poor). All of these variables were expressed as percentages. Lastly, in order to consider the spatial dimension of each territorial units (i.e. enumeration area) in the vulnerability investigation, we also included the spatial variables linked to centroid coordinates (X, Y) of the enumeration areas computed by QGIS (3.32 version) (Lapietra et al., 2025).

Table 1 Variables and data sources used for hazard assessment, exposure calculation and vulnerability evaluation with indication of the data source. EA = Enumeration Area

RISK COMPONENT	SUB-COMPONENT	VARIABLE	DATA SOURCE
Hazard	<i>Volcanic</i>	1. Flow temperature 2. Particle volumetric concentration 3. Flow duration 4. Flow dynamic pressure	<i>Mele et al., 2024</i>
Exposure	<i>Population</i>	1. N° of inhabitants	<i>ISTAT 2021</i>
	<i>Building</i>	1. N° of buildings	<i>DPC 2021</i>

Vulnerability	<i>Social</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Younger with age <15 years 2. Elderly with age > 64 years 3. Foreign residents 4. Households with members > 4 5. Low human capital (males) 6. Low human capital (females) 7. Unemployed males 8. Unemployed females 9. EA centroid X coordinate 10. EA centroid Y coordinate 	<i>ISTAT 2021</i>
	<i>Physical</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Residential buildings 2. Commercial buildings 3. Buildings constructed with masonry material 4. Buildings constructed with other material 5. Buildings < 1919 6. 1919 < Building < 1945 7. 1946 < Building < 1960 8. 1961 < Building < 1979 9. 1971 < Building < 1979 10. Buildings with more than 4 floors 11. Buildings in poor condition 12. Buildings in very poor condition 13. EA centroid X coordinate 14. EA centroid Y coordinate 	<i>ISTAT 2011</i>

4. Activities – the steps toward the integrated multidimensional framework

To assess volcanic risk at the EA level in the Vesuvius region, a combination of Geographic Information System (GIS) and statistical techniques was employed to develop an integrated multidimensional framework using QGIS and SPSS software. Figure 2 illustrates the hazard-dependent approach adopted for this analysis. Starting from the volcanic hazard assessment (light orange), information on exposure (light green) and vulnerability (light violet) within the potentially affected area was derived to map the overall volcanic risk.

Specifically, the PDCs impact parameters (Table 1), mapped on a regular grid at 250m resolution (Dellino et al., 2025), were first standardized and subjected to factor analysis (FA) to extract the main factor explaining the entire dataset. As only four variables were considered, the extracted factor was defined as “volcanic hazard index” and mapped on the same grid. Because this index had to be integrated with the subsequent risk components (exposure and vulnerability) at the EA level, the grid map was converted to match the 2021 ISTAT EA boundaries. The resulting vector data were then transformed into raster format and rescaled from 1 (very low hazard) to 5 (very high hazard).

Once the volcanic hazard was mapped, municipalities and corresponding EAs were intersected to retrieve exposure and vulnerability data from ISTAT and DPC datasets (Table 1). Following Figure 2, the exposure component was analyzed through two sub-components: population exposure and building exposure. Population exposure was

calculated by measuring population density in each EA, expressed as the ratio between the number of inhabitants and the total EA area. EAs with zero population were excluded. The resulting vector data were converted into raster format and rescaled from 1 (very low population exposure) to 5 (very high population exposure). For building exposure, building density was computed by extracting building centroids from the building shapefile to count the number of buildings within each EA, then dividing by the EA area. EAs with zero buildings were likewise excluded. The results were converted into raster format and rescaled from 1 (very low building exposure) to 5 (very high building exposure). Total exposure was then obtained using the QGIS Raster Calculator tool by summing population and building exposure layers, with the final raster rescaled from 1 (very low exposure) to 5 (very high exposure).

Social vulnerability was derived through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) applied to standardized demographic and socio-economic variables (Table 1). For each EA, factor scores were weighted by multiplying them by the percentage of variance explained by each factor and dividing by the total variance (Siagian et al., 2014; Frigerio et al., 2016). The composite Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) was then calculated using Equation 1:

$$SVI = \frac{(Factor1 * Variance1) + (Factor2 * Variance2) + (FactorN * VarianceN)}{Tot. Variance}$$

The results were mapped, converted to raster, and rescaled from 1 (very low social vulnerability) to 5 (very high social vulnerability). Building vulnerability for each EA was computed following the same procedure and using Equation 1 to generate the Physical Vulnerability Index (PVI). Because the underlying variables referred to 2011 EAs (Table 1), a cartographic transposition from 2011 to 2021 ISTAT boundaries was performed in QGIS. The resulting vector was converted to raster and rescaled from 1 (very low physical vulnerability) to 5 (very high physical vulnerability). Overall vulnerability was then calculated with the QGIS Raster Calculator by summing the social and physical vulnerability layers, and the final raster was rescaled from 1 to 5.

Finally, volcanic risk was estimated by multiplying the hazard, exposure, and vulnerability layers using the same tool. The resulting raster was reclassified through quantile classification into five categories: 1 (very low volcanic risk), 2 (low), 3 (medium), 4 (high), and 5 (very high). This classification also enabled the extraction of information on the number of inhabitants and buildings within each risk class.

Figure 2 Operational workflow for volcanic risk analysis based on the definition described in section 1. For DATA INPUT please refer to Table 1. Symbol + represents a sum, while

symbol x represents a multiplication. EA = enumeration area; SVI = social vulnerability index; PVI = Physical vulnerability index.

5.RESULTS

The spatial distribution of the volcanic hazard index intercepts an area of 432 km² which includes 43 municipalities and 6608 EAs (Figure 1) with a total population of 1 075 508 inhabitants and 100 804 buildings (Table 2).

Figure 3 Study area intercepted by the volcanic hazard index map grid (left-bottom) with the identification of the municipalities and EAs possibly affect. The ISTAT boundaries refer to the year 2021 and were retrieved from <https://www.istat.it/notizia/basi-territoriali-e-variabili-censuarie/>.

Table 2 Municipalities under investigation with number of EAs, inhabitants (POP21) and buildings (BUILD21) referring to the year 2021 intercepted by the hazard index grid map.

	MUNICIPALITY	N.° of EA21	POP21	BUILD21
1	ACERRA	118	15 360	1 312
2	AFRAGOLA	487	61 593	3 252
3	ARZANO	28	2 689	608
4	BOSCOREALE	247	26 317	3 569
5	BOSCOTRECASE	74	9 897	1 556
6	BRUSCIANO	95	1 5851	1 448
7	CAIVANO	1	1	13

8	CARDITO	11	2 696	163
9	CASALNUOVO DI NAPOLI	198	47 428	2 716
10	CASAVATORE	67	18 282	610
11	CASORIA	321	74 394	4 108
12	CASTELLAMARE DI STABIA	9	3 296	181
13	CASTELLO DI CISTERNA	78	7 815	1 270
14	CERCOLA	76	17 124	1 401
15	FRATTAMAGGIORE	8	434	46
16	MARIGLIANELLA	9	1 628	117
17	MARIGLIANO	57	6 725	1 702
18	NAPOLI	1 288	160 648	12 224
19	NOLA	78	5677	1 175
20	OTTAVIANO	132	23 064	3 804
21	PALMA CAMPANIA	8	257	82
22	POGGIOMARINO	72	21 504	1 971
23	POLLENA TROCCHIA	73	12 976	1 915
24	POMIGLIANO D'ARCO	318	39 762	2 963
25	POMPEI	187	22 339	3 007
26	PORTICI	190	52 500	1 863
27	ERCOLANO	297	50 580	5 054
28	SAN GENNARO VESUVIANO	46	11 714	1 669
29	SAN GIORGIO A CREMANO	186	43 057	1 346
30	SAN GIUSEPPE VESUVIANO	105	30 045	3 893
31	SAN SEBASTIANO AL VESUVIO	54	8721	1 142
32	SANT'ANASTASIA	284	26 460	3 605
33	SAN VITALIANO	1	6	6
34	SAVIANO	25	5 960	1 643
35	SCISCIANO	28	3 095	975
36	SOMMA VESUVIANA	193	33 935	6 474
37	TERZIGNO	72	17 256	3 177
38	TORRE ANNUNZIATA	206	40 523	2 204
39	TORRE DEL GRECO	477	81 289	8 149
40	VOLLA	119	25 369	2 552
41	TRECASE	70	8 594	1 687
42	MASSA DI SOMMA	30	5 056	1 268
43	SCAFATI	185	33 591	2 884
	TOTAL	6 608	1 075 508	100 804

Figure 4 shows the volcanic hazard level distribution across the EAs under investigations, where 1 corresponds to very low hazard, 2 to low hazard, 3 to medium hazard, 4 to high hazard and 5 to very high hazard. The map highlights that the highest hazard levels (4 and 5) occur in EAs located near the volcano, particularly within municipalities of Sant'Anastasia, Pollena Trocchia, Somma Vesuviana, Ottaviano, and Massa di Somma with level 5 extending in the northwestern direction. Hazard levels gradually decrease with increasing distance from the volcano, reaching the lowest levels (1 and 2) near the outer

boundaries of the study area. Consequently, municipalities that extend from the slopes of Mt Vesuvius down to lower-altitude coastal zones — including Napoli, Ercolano, and Torre del Greco — may encompass the full range of volcanic hazard levels. Looking at Table 3, most of the municipalities (67%) shows EAs with very low volcanic hazard level (level 1), 48 % is characterized by medium level (level 3), 46 % by low (level 2) and high (level 4) levels while 37 % of municipalities present very high level of volcanic hazard (level 5). As shown in the same table, almost half of the municipalities under investigation are characterized by the highest volcanic hazard levels (4 and 5).

Figure 4 Spatial distribution of volcanic hazard across the municipalities under investigation at enumeration area level.

Table 3 Volcanic hazard levels of EAs included in each municipality under investigation. Municipalities underlined with yellow color show the highest level of volcanic hazard.

MUNICIPALITY	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	LEVEL 4	LEVEL 5
ACERRA	X	X	X		
AFRAGOLA	X	X	X	X	
ARZANO	X				
BOSCOREALE	X	X	X	X	
BOSCOTRECASE			X	X	X

BRUSCIANO	X	X			
CAIVANO	X				
CARDITO	X				
CASALNUOVO DI NAPOLI			X	X	X
CASAVATORE	X				
CASORIA	X	X	X	X	
CASTELLAMARE DI STABIA	X	X			
CASTELLO DI CISTERNA	X	X	X		
CERCOLA					X
FRATTAMAGGIORE	X				
MARIGLIANELLA	X				
MARIGLIANO	X				
NAPOLI	X	X	X	X	X
NOLA	X	X	X		
OTTAVIANO	X	X	X	X	X
PALMA CAMPANIA	X				
POGGIOMARINO	X	X			
POLLENA TROCCHIA					X
POMIGLIANO D'ARCO			X	X	X
POMPEI		X	X	X	
PORTICI	X	X	X	X	
ERCOLANO	X	X	X	X	X
SAN GENNARO VESUVIANO	X				
SAN GIORGIO A CREMANO		X	X	X	
SAN GIUSEPPE VESUVIANO		X	X	X	X
SAN SEBASTIANO AL VESUVIO				X	X
SANT'ANASTASIA					X
SAN VITALIANO	X				
SAVIANO	X				
SCISCIANO	X				
SOMMA VESUVIANA	X	X	X	X	X
TERZIGNO		X	X	X	X
TORRE ANNUNZIATA	X	X	X	X	
TORRE DEL GRECO	X	X	X	X	X
VOLLA				X	X
TRECASE			X	X	
MASSA DI SOMMA					X
SCAFATI	X				

5.1 Exposure

Figure 4 shows the results of the exposure assessment, illustrating the spatial distribution of population density (Figure 4A), building density (Figure 4B), and overall exposure (Figure 4C). Exposure levels are classified from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high). As observed in the maps, the lowest exposure levels (1 and 2) are mainly found in EAs located near the volcano and, more generally, in the northeastern portion of the study area. In contrast, exposure hotspots characterized by levels 4 and 5 are primarily clustered within coastal

municipalities such as Portici, San Giorgio a Cremano, Napoli, and Ercolano, as well as in the western sector of the study area.

Table 4 summarizes the distribution of exposure levels across the municipalities under investigation. The results indicate that the majority of municipalities exhibit medium (level 3; 95%) and high (level 4; 93%) exposure, followed by very high exposure (level 5; 79%), low exposure (level 2; 74%), and very low exposure (level 1; 23%). Notably, approximately 80% of the municipalities—highlighted in yellow in Table 4—are characterized by the highest level of exposure

Figure 5 Spatial distribution of population (A), building (B) and overall (C) exposure across the municipalities under investigation at enumeration area level.

Table 4 Overall exposure levels of EAs included in each municipality under investigation.

MUNICIPALITY	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	LEVEL 4	LEVEL 5
ACERRA	X	X	X	X	X
AFRAGOLA		X	X	X	
ARZANO		X	X	X	X
BOSCOREALE		X	X	X	
BOSCOTRECASE		X	X	X	X
BRUSCIANO		X	X	X	X
CAIVANO	X				
CARDITO			X	X	X
CASALNUOVO DI NAPOLI		X	X	X	X
CASAVATORE			X	X	X
CASORIA		X	X	X	X
CASTELLAMARE DI STABIA			X	X	

CASTELLO DI CISTERNA	X	X	X	X	X
CERCOLA			X	X	X
FRATTAMAGGIORE		X	X		
MARIGLIANELLA			X	X	X
MARIGLIANO		X	X	X	X
NAPOLI		X	X	X	X
NOLA	X	X	X	X	X
OTTAVIANO	X	X	X	X	X
PALMA CAMPANIA		X	X	X	
POGGIOMARINO	X	X	X	X	X
POLLENA TROCCHIA		X	X	X	X
POMIGLIANO D'ARCO		X	X	X	X
POMPEI		X	X	X	X
PORTICI		X	X	X	
ERCOLANO	X	X	X	X	X
SAN GENNARO VESUVIANO		X	X	X	X
SAN GIORGIO A CREMANO		X	X	X	X
SAN GIUSEPPE VESUVIANO		X	X	X	X
SAN SEBASTIANO AL VESUVIO			X	X	X
SANT'ANASTASIA		X	X	X	X
SAN VITALIANO	X				
SAVIANO		X	X	X	X
SCISCIANO		X	X	X	X
SOMMA VESUVIANA		X	X	X	X
TERZIGNO	X	X	X	X	X
TORRE ANNUNZIATA		X	X	X	X
TORRE DEL GRECO	X	X	X	X	X
VOLLA			X	X	X
TRECASE			X	X	X
MASSA DI SOMMA			X	X	X
SCAFATI		X	X	X	X

5.2 Vulnerability

Figure 6 illustrates the spatial distribution of social (Figure 6A), physical (Figure 6B), and overall (Figure 6C) vulnerability levels. The classification scheme ranges from level 1 (very low vulnerability) to level 5 (very high vulnerability). As observed in the maps, the lowest vulnerability levels (1 and 2) are predominantly found in EAs located in the southeastern portion of the study area, particularly within the municipalities of Scafati, Terzigno, Pompei, and Palma Campania. Conversely, EAs situated in the western sector of the volcanic area exhibit higher vulnerability levels (3, 4, and 5), notably within the municipalities of Sant'Anastasia, Volla, Portici, and Afragola.

Consistently with the other risk components, Table 5 shows the distribution of overall vulnerability levels across the municipalities under investigation. The results indicate that the majority of municipalities (83%) are characterized by high vulnerability (level 4),

followed by medium (level 3; 81%), low (level 2; 81%), and very low (level 1; 79%) vulnerability levels. Moreover, more than half of the municipalities (62%) contain EAs associated with the highest degree of vulnerability (level 5).

Figure 6 Spatial distribution of social (A), physical (B) and overall (C) vulnerability across the municipalities under investigation at enumeration area level.

Table 5 Overall vulnerability levels of EAs included in each municipality under investigation.

MUNICIPALITY	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	LEVEL 4	LEVEL 5
ACERRA	X	X	X	X	X
AFRAGOLA	X	X	X	X	X
ARZANO			X	X	X
BOSCOREALE	X	X	X	X	
BOSCOTRECASE	X	X	X	X	
BRUSCIANO	X	X	X	X	X
CAIVANO				X	
CARDITO				X	X
CASALNUOVO DI NAPOLI	X	X	X	X	X
CASAVATORE		X	X	X	X
CASORIA	X	X	X	X	X
CASTELLAMARE DI STABIA	X				
CASTELLO DI CISTERNA	X	X	X	X	X
CERCOLA	X	X	X	X	X
FRATTAMAGGIORE					X
MARIGLIANELLA					X
MARIGLIANO		X	X	X	X
NAPOLI	X	X	X	X	X

NOLA	X	X	X	X	X
OTTAVIANO	X	X	X	X	X
PALMA CAMPANIA	X				
POGGIOMARINO	X	X	X	X	
POLLENA TROCCHIA	X	X	X	X	X
POMIGLIANO D'ARCO	X	X	X	X	X
POMPEI	X	X	X		
PORTICI	X	X	X	X	X
ERCOLANO	X	X	X	X	X
SAN GENNARO VESUVIANO	X	X	X		
SAN GIORGIO A CREMANO	X	X	X	X	X
SAN GIUSEPPE VESUVIANO	X	X	X	X	
SAN SEBASTIANO AL VESUVIO	X	X	X	X	
SANT'ANASTASIA	X	X	X	X	X
SAN VITALIANO		X			
SAVIANO		X	X	X	
SCISCIANO	X	X	X	X	
SOMMA VESUVIANA	X	X	X	X	X
TERZIGNO	X	X	X	X	
TORRE ANNUNZIATA	X	X	X	X	X
TORRE DEL GRECO	X	X	X	X	X
VOLLA	X	X	X	X	X
TRECASE	X	X	X	X	
MASSA DI SOMMA	X	X	X	X	X
SCAFATI	X				

5.3 Volcanic risk

Figure 7 illustrates the final results derived from the integration of volcanic hazard, exposure, and vulnerability indicators, depicting the spatial distribution of volcanic risk levels across the examined EAs. The classification ranges from 1 (very low volcanic risk) to 5 (very high volcanic risk). Overall, the map reveals that EAs characterized by the highest risk levels (4 and 5), represented in red, are predominantly concentrated in the northwestern portion of the study area—particularly within the municipalities of Sant’Anastasia, Volla, Cercola, San Sebastiano al Vesuvio, and along the coastal municipalities of Ercolano, Portici, and Napoli. Conversely, lower risk levels are primarily distributed around the volcano and throughout the eastern sectors of the study area.

As reported in Table 6, the majority of municipalities (81%) contain EAs with low volcanic risk (level 2), followed by 76% with medium risk (level 3), 74% with high risk (level 4), and 67% with very low risk (level 1). Furthermore, 24% of municipalities exhibit EAs with very high volcanic risk (level 5). Notably, nearly half of the municipalities under investigation are characterized by high to very high volcanic risk levels (levels 4 and 5).

Figure 7 Spatial distribution of volcanic risk levels across the municipalities under investigation at enumeration area level.

Table 6 Volcanic risk levels of EAs included in each municipality under investigation

MUNICIPALITY	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	LEVEL 4	LEVEL 5
ACERRA	X	X	X	X	X
AFRAGOLA	X	X	X	X	X
ARZANO	X	X	X		
BOSCOREALE	X	X	X	X	X
BOSCOTRECASE		X	X	X	X
BRUSCIANO	X	X	X	X	X
CAIVANO	X			X	
CARDITO		X	X		
CASALNUOVO DI NAPOLI			X	X	X
CASAVATORE	X	X	X	X	
CASORIA		X	X	X	X
CASTELLAMARE DI STABIA	X	X			
CASTELLO DI CISTERNA	X	X	X	X	X
CERCOLA				X	X
FRATTAMAGGIORE	X	X			

MARIGLIANELLA			X		
MARIGLIANO	X	X	X	X	
NAPOLI	X	X	X	X	X
NOLA	X	X	X		
OTTAVIANO	X	X	X	X	X
PALMA CAMPANIA	X				
POGGIOMARINO		X	X	X	
POLLENA TROCCHIA	X	X	X	X	X
POMIGLIANO D'ARCO		X	X	X	X
POMPEI	X	X	X	X	
PORTICI	X	X	X	X	X
ERCOLANO	X	X	X	X	X
SAN GENNARO VESUVIANO	X	X			
SAN GIORGIO A CREMANO		X	X	X	X
SAN GIUSEPPE VESUVIANO	X	X	X	X	
SAN SEBASTIANO AL VESUVIO		X	X	X	
SANT'ANASTASIA		X	X	X	X
SAN VITALIANO	X				
SAVIANO	X	X	X		
SCISCIANO	X	X	X	X	
SOMMA VESUVIANA	X	X	X	X	X
TERZIGNO	X	X	X	X	X
TORRE ANNUNZIATA	X	X	X	X	X
TORRE DEL GRECO	X	X	X	X	X
VOLLA				X	X
TRECASE		X	X	X	X
MASSA DI SOMMA				X	X
SCAFATI	X	X			

6. Conclusion

For the first time, an innovative method based on multivariate statistics coupled with cartographic techniques was used on the test case of Vesuvius for mapping the areal distribution of volcanic risk by means of a synthetic index. The further use of the PoC even for other natural risks, can help prioritize areas in need of targeted strategies to promote sustainable development, disaster preparedness, and resilience. The results are presented in form of maps, while tables are provided to show the hazard, exposure, vulnerability and risk characteristics in each municipality under investigation. The PoC provides a clear and simplified methodology for researcher and stakeholders who work in the field of disaster risk reduction, risk analysis, emergency planning and mitigation strategies.

7. Stakeholders

The further application of the PoC can be of interest to stakeholders having interest in the field of insurance, mitigation activities and education

8. Transferability

While the PoC was tested on volcanic risk at Vesuvius, the methodology can be extended to all the risks that have a geographical distribution around highly populated areas

8. Progress Status

In progress

X Completed

9. Contact Person

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